

DESIGNING A SHARED DIGITAL PRESERVATION LAB FOR NATIONAL LIBRARY AND ARCHIVES NEW ZEALAND

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Abstract - In 2019, Te Rua Mahara o te Kāwanatanga Archives New Zealand and Te Puna Mātauranga o Aotearoa National Library of New Zealand began planning the design and build of a new shared Digital Preservation Lab for the two organisations. The Digital Preservation Lab would be part of a major capital works project to build a new purpose-built Archives building due for completion in late 2025. It was essential to understand each other's workflows and equipment needs and co-design to the space to ensure that the Digital Preservation Lab would meet the needs of both organisations and their digital preservation and digital archiving teams.

This paper will trace the journey spanning over half a decade to envision and plan the Digital Preservation Lab for Archives and the National Library and the decision-making process behind it. It will also detail the equipment chosen, and the setup for the facility as a potential model for other institutions to use.

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I. INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Te Tari Taiwhenua, the Department of Internal Affairs (DIA) for the New Zealand Government, is responsible for a vast collection of records, data, publications, archives and manuscripts, images, and audiovisual recordings.

Te Rua Mahara o te Kāwanatanga Archives New Zealand (referred to here as 'Archives' or ANZ) oversees New Zealand's record of government under the Public Records Act of 2005. Aotearoa New Zealand's nation's non-governmental documentary heritage is cared for under the auspices of Te Puna Mātauranga o Aotearoa National Library of New Zealand (referred to here as 'National Library,' or NLNZ). Both Archives and National Library operated as autonomous government agencies until 2011, when they were each integrated into DIA's Information and Knowledge Services branch. In 2025, Archives and National Library underwent a functional alignment, where the previously distinct organisations joined together under shared leadership of the Chief Archivist Poumanaaki and National Librarian Te Pouhuaki [1].

Although digital preservation programmes had existed at National Library and Archives for nearly 20 years, neither institution had an ideal space for storage and use of legacy computer hardware and software. Digital teams and individual staff members compiled their own troves of computer equipment and peripherals over the years, often kept alongside their own workstations, or stashed away wherever space was available.

In November 2016, a 7.8 magnitude earthquake struck Wellington, centred in Kaikōura in New Zealand's South Island. Archives New Zealand's

building was damaged and closed to both staff and the public for several months. The digital preservation equipment at Archives New Zealand needed to be relocated urgently for building repairs to commence.

In May 2017, initial funding was approved to design a new purpose-built archival facility for Archives New Zealand in Wellington. The new archival building would be adjacent to the National Library and connected with a link bridge, forming the heart of a national documentary heritage campus. The building would include secure collections loading and quarantine areas, state-of-the-art repositories and shelving, audio visual and film suites, conservation, and digitisation facilities, as well as a dedicated digital preservation lab. Digital preservation and digital archiving are often siloed from each other, even though they have similar technical needs. Having a shared space for digital preservation activities would allow staff across the institutions to work more collaboratively and break down silos. However, staff would need to develop new workflows and protocols for using the space and ensure that the Lab was adaptable enough to meet the needs of both organisations.

II. DIGITAL PRESERVATION LAB FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

The proposed Digital Preservation Lab would be shared by staff across three departments: Archives New Zealand's System Strategy and Standards Team (who process the digital transfer and management of government public records in the Government Digital Archive, or GDA); the Library's Digital Preservation and Data Capability Team (responsible for the National Digital Heritage Archive, or NDHA) including the full array of the Library's born-digital and digitised collections, including web archives and whole of .nz domain crawls; and the Library's Digital Archivists who manage incoming unpublished born-digital archives and special collections, mainly donated by members of the public.

While all engage with digital preservation activities, each team has its own areas of focus and types of collections worked on. Both the NDHA and GDA digital repositories use Rosetta software, for example, but the ingest tools used by each organisation are bespoke. The NDHA and GDA Rosetta instances have each been configured in ways most appropriate to their specific collections, with different levels of access, user permissions, and

customisation in place. Furthermore, multiple collection/archival management systems interact with Rosetta to provide metadata for digital objects, depending on whether a digital object is stored in the GDA or NDHA. The Lab's design and setup needed to support a variety of digital preservation workflows, tools, and functions. The Library's digital archivists are expected to be working in the Lab most days, whereas the Library's Digital Preservation and Data Capability team and Archives New Zealand's digital preservation team are expected to work in the space on an ad hoc basis.

The main functions identified for the Lab were:

1) To provide a safe, secure space for both collections and staff. It also needed to have secure network capability to allow for large digital transfers, separate from the main corporate network for security assessment ahead of transferring digital content to the GDA or NDHA.

2) That the lab be suitable both for storage, as well as active use, of legacy computers and specialist digital preservation equipment and setups.

3) That a range of digital preservation activities could be performed in the space, with appropriate setup for the quarantine, appraisal, transfer or transformation and access of digital media items.

4) To provide a dedicated space for hands-on training and upskilling of staff across Aotearoa's GLAMIR (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums, Iwi (Māori tribes), and Records community, with a suite of equipment and specialist software available.

The Lab had another perceived value - for digital preservation advocacy. The Lab could also be a tool for showcasing digital preservation work which would otherwise go unseen. Having a dedicated working space for digital preservation equipment would allow both internal and external stakeholders to better understand the significance of the Library and Archives' digital preservation work. The Lab could also serve as a potential resource for government agencies to take their legacy digital content for analysis and retrieval.

In planning sessions there were sometimes competing views of what the Lab could and should be used for. The ideal was to have a flexible and dynamic space, which could serve a variety of purposes - business as usual collection processing; a controlled space for triaging challenging digital file

formats; and futureproofing the lab to be able to handle ever-increasing volumes of digital content.

III. ROOM DESIGN, INFRASTRUCTURE, AND FURNISHINGS

In terms of room design, staff advocated for a practical, yet flexible configuration. The room had space for twelve workstations, plus two mobile tables. The workstations would be connected by soft wiring that could be separated and moved readily. The preference was for all services to remain exposed, with cabling and ducting visible and accessible above. The Lab would have network and power cabling to workstations by two drop-down umbilicals at the workstations closest to the entrance. The Lab would have standard overhead lighting, with task lighting available on workbenches to facilitate detail work, such as assembling and disassembling hardware.

Functionally, the room needed to have ample space for trolleys and collection items to move freely, with wide doorways. Furthermore, the room needed soundproofing, fire suppression, and appropriate computer racking and cooling. In terms of infrastructure, the Lab needed multiple network points and power points at benches and along walls. The more power outlets, the better.

The Lab would include sit-stand workstations, standard office chairs, mobile benches, built-in shelving, and ample storage. It was important to have some dedicated workstations for specialist equipment, such as the FRED, which would remain set up at all times and be able to be used by multiple staff. However, digital preservation staff also highlighted the need for space to set up laptops and computers on an as-needed basis, with clear tables and workspaces available.

Designing the ICT setup for the Lab was one of the biggest challenges right from the start. The Library and Archives' IT requirements are significantly different than the standard IT office setup. The Lab needed access to the non-corporate network (known colloquially as LABNET), with firewalls and security measures in place, to protect against any potentially dangerous files that might be present among digital transfers. Staff identified high-speed data connection to the NDHA, GDA, and network-attached storage (NAS) as a make-or-break criteria for the Lab's success. Some of the ICT options initially suggested for the Lab were not suitable for digital preservation workflows. DIA preferred Zero

Trust Network (ZTN) and Cloud Managed Internet Only (CMIO) solutions; however, legacy equipment often cannot authenticate in this way. The building itself would not have physical network cables and would be Wi-Fi by default. Both Digital Preservation and Audio-Visual Conservation staff expressed concerns that this would impact the speed and efficiency for large file transfers.

Because the Lab needed the separate LABNET network to protect the main corporate network, digital files would need to be transferred twice – first to the network-attached storage on the untrusted LABNET, where they would be isolated for initial analysis, technical appraisal, and assessment. Then, once appraisal and assessment were complete, the files to be retained would be copied to a portable drive and then copied again to the trusted corporate network and ingested into Rosetta's permanent digital storage. Once teams are working in the space, this workflow will be reviewed and adapted as required.

IV. SPECIALIST EQUIPMENT

The digital preservation Lab was part of a major works project, so there was a healthy budget for the purchase of new furniture and equipment, including the ability to replace some of our current equipment with the latest models. We identified the following equipment as a priority for the Lab:

- Network-attached storage (NAS) with up to 150 TB storage capacity.
- MacBook Pro and Mac Mini M4 Pro devices for processing Mac-formatted digital collections.
- Ultra Bay 4 Portable which could be used on or offsite to allow for flexibility with processing legacy disk interfaces.
- Atola Insights DS2 – a disk imaging plus diagnostics and file system identification tool
- HP Z2 Tower workstations, including at least one with advanced GPU for offline local artificial intelligence (AI) capabilities.
- Uninterruptable Power Supply (UPS).
- ZuluSCSI computer storage emulation platform.
- KryoFlux forensic floppy controller.
- Greaseweazle forensic floppy controller.
- Monitors with obsolete connections for legacy devices.
- Write-blocker kits with a variety of inputs.

Staff also identified smaller but useful items, such as a soldiering iron kit, mini-network cable tester, magnifying lamp, long nose pliers, screwdriver kit, electronic repair kits, and anti-static mats for task work. The Lab would also need basic supplies and consumable items, such as a label maker and tape, zip ties, Velcro tape, wire cutters, and cabling to install and maintain equipment.

V. PHYSICAL STORAGE

Both NLNZ and ANZ hold a range of vintage computers and specialist equipment, including a Forensic Recovery of Evidence Device (FRED), Kryoflux floppy disk readers, a Nimble optical disc robot, and an array of early Mac and Windows machines [2]. These tools were stored in disparate locations across the Library and Archives. The most unique and high value items held by the Library and Archives' digital preservation and digital archivist teams were listed in digital preservation equipment inventories; however, we needed to understand exactly how much digital equipment there was, and how much storage space would be required for it all to be centralised.

Digital Preservation staff across Library and Archives needed to identify and inventory their own equipment and storage needs. This meant literally using tape measures to calculate the total linear metres of equipment from all those cupboards, tambors, workspaces, storage closets, and more. In the end, each organisation had a surprisingly similar amount of equipment storage needs – Archives identified 44 linear metres of shelving required for their equipment, and the National Library 45 linear metres. The Lab contains 117.5 linear metres of in-built joinery for storage, which will allow for some growth; however, rationalisation of duplicate or non-essential equipment will still be required.

VI. CONCLUSION

The new shared Digital Preservation Lab for Te Rua Mahara o te Kāwanatanga Archives New Zealand and Te Puna Mātauranga o Aotearoa National Library of New Zealand is an exciting step forward in our institutions' digital preservation journey. By having a dedicated space for both legacy equipment, as well as current digital preservation research, such as Large Language Model (LLM) experimentation and data preservation, we are ensuring that our institutions will be able to continue to safeguard and

preserve Aotearoa New Zealand's digital cultural heritage and public record into the future.

Despite careful planning, we know that we will not have gotten everything right. There will be a period of disruption to our usual work as we move and set up the equipment, and test and commission the space. The work of installing and testing each piece of new equipment will need to be performed by staff on the digital preservation teams, as it is non-standard ICT and requires specialist knowledge. All going well, the digital preservation lab will be operational by November 2025. We hope that sharing our journey to plan and design this space will be helpful to other institutions for envisioning their own digital preservation workspaces.

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